

Empowering Ischemic Stroke Risk Assessment: A DNA-Based Lateral Flow Assay for miRNA-638 Detection

Ana Rubio-Monterde,^{a,b,±} Lourdes Rivas,^a Marc Gallegos,^a Josep M. Aran,^c Daniel Quesada-González^{a,b,±,*} & Arben Merkoçi^{a,b,d,e,*}

^a Paperdrop Diagnostics S.L., MRB building, Campus UAB, 08193 Bellaterra, Spain

^b Nanobioelectronics and Biosensors Group, Catalan Institute of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology (ICN2), CSIC, Barcelona, Spain

^c Immune-inflammatory Processes and Gene Therapeutics Group, IDIBELL, L'Hospitalet de Llobregat, 08908 Barcelona, Spain

^d The Barcelona Institute of Science and Technology (BIST), Campus UAB, 08036 Bellaterra, Barcelona, Spain

^e ICREA, Institució Catalana de Recerca i Estudis Avançats, Pg. Lluís Companys 23, 08010, Barcelona, Spain

*Corresponding authors: daniel.quesada@icn2.cat, arben.merkoci@icn2.cat

± Both authors contributed equally.

ABSTRACT

The potential of miRNA-638 holds promising implications for ischemic stroke risk assessment. Preliminary findings reveal its role in vascular smooth muscle cells and implication on proliferative vascular diseases. This work introduces the first DNA-based lateral flow test for miRNA-638 detection. Unlike conventional PCR-based methods, this innovation marries sensitivity with accessibility, negating the need for specialized personnel and costly equipment. Employing a lateral flow chromatographic reader for precise quantification, we established our detection limit at 0.14 nM of miRNA-638. This advancement not only surmounts current limitations, but also streamlines the diagnostic process (response is obtained in less than 15 min), potentially revolutionizing the future of ischemic stroke risk assessment. The presented assay represents a significant leap towards democratizing miRNA analysis, marking a milestone in the field of biosensors and bioelectronics.

Keywords: Lateral Flow; Ischemic Stroke; Nanoparticles; miRNA; Point-of-Care; Diagnostic.

1. Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), cerebrovascular accidents (a.k.a. brain strokes) are the second cause of death in the world and the third source of disability.¹ 87% of these cerebrovascular accidents are classified as ischemic strokes,² meaning that the blood supply to the brain is blocked, causing ischemia, usually by a blood clot or atherosclerosis. Atherosclerosis is the build-up of a plaque in the artery walls. When this plaque is vulnerable, there is an increased risk of stroke. This increased risk is evaluated through imaging techniques (e.g. contrast-enhanced ultrasound)³ that have elevated costs and are only applicable in advanced stages of the disease. Thus, novel diagnostic markers for non-invasive anticipation of ischemic stroke are needed.

MicroRNAs (miRNAs) are small non-coding RNAs, 21-25 nucleotides long, that have an important role in gene expression regulation.⁴ miRNAs are emerging as non-invasive biomarkers for a variety of diseases such as cancer, endometriosis or cardiovascular and infectious diseases.⁵⁻¹² Following this trend, a clinical prospective study showed the correlation of low levels of miRNA-638 with plaque vulnerability and the risk of suffering an ischemic stroke.^{13,14} It was observed that in patients who suffered an ischemic stroke the concentration of this circulating miRNA in blood decreased.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the working principle of the DNA-based LF for the detection of miRNA-638. The miRNA is captured in a sandwich between 2 single-strained DNA probes complementary to part of its sequence according to Watson-Crick base pairing and leading to the appearance of the TL.

Current preferred miRNA detection methods are Northern blotting, RT-qPCR or next generation sequencing (NGS).¹⁵ These techniques, although highly sensitive, rely on qualified personnel and expensive equipment. The increasing interest in miRNA detection for diagnostic applications comes with an increasing demand of cheaper, faster and easier detection tools, specially at point-of-care (PoC).¹⁶ Among the different devices for PoC testing, rapid diagnostic tests (RDT) have become very popular during the last two years due the COVID-19 pandemic,^{17,18} especially those based on lateral flow (LF) paper-based technology.¹⁹⁻²²

LF tests stand for their portability, easiness-of-use, fast response and low-cost production. Furthermore, the inclusion of nanomaterials on these tests makes them very versatile and tuneable,²³⁻²⁵ allowing even the semi quantification of the response, either by naked-eye or with a colorimetric reader. This quantification could be even carried out by a standard home scanner²⁶ or by a smartphone.^{27,28} Although LF systems are often imagined as immunoassays (i.e. standard designs rely on antibodies for recognition), it has been demonstrated that DNA-based LF tests (a.k.a. molecular LF tests) are also functional.²⁹⁻³⁴

Herein we introduce a DNA-based LF assay for the recognition of miRNA-638 biomarker which, as we said, can be related with the risk of suffering an ischemic stroke.¹³ As far as our knowledge is concerned, we report for the first time a LF test able to detect miRNA-638 in just 15 min using amino-labelled DNA probes²⁶ and, although we compare the readout between a standard home scanner and a LF colorimetric reader for quantitative purposes, no equipment would actually be necessary to read our paper strips.

Our LF strips design (represented in Fig. 1) is composed by four pads:^{23,25} the sample pad, where the test sample is dropped; the conjugate pad, which houses gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) conjugated with a single-strained capture DNA probe; the detection pad, where recognition (detailed in section 2.4) takes place; and the absorbent pad, designed to soak up any remaining liquid.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials and reagents

Cellulose fibre, laminated cards and glass fibre from Millipore (CFSP001700, HF000MC100 and GFDX000800, respectively); higher protein binding nitrocellulose membrane from MDI membrane technologies (CNPC-SS12-10 μm); HAuCl_4 , sodium citrate, boric acid, sodium tetraborate, bovine serum albumin, sucrose and Tween 20 from Scharlab (22362, SO01990500, AC05771000, 206291000, 26813, 22090 and TW00220100, respectively); tris-buffered saline tablets, saline-sodium citrate buffer, OmniPur CHAPS, betaine and tris (2-carboxyethyl) phosphine from Merck (T8280, S6639, 3050-OP, B2629 and T8280, respectively); and different custom DNA probes and miRNA from Integrated DNA Technologies.

2.2. Instruments

Continuous Reagent Dispenser and Programmable Strip Cutter from Shanghai Kinbio Tech (HM8008 and ZQ2002, respectively); HP DeskJet Plus scanner (4100 series); drying oven from Mestra (80118); Immunochromato Lateral Flow Reader from Hamamatsu (C10066-10); UV-Vis Spectrophotometer from Molecular Devices (SpectraMax iD3); Thermoshaker from Labnet (EQN022); Biocen Centrifuge from Orto Alresta (model 22R); and transmission electron microscope from JEOL (1210), located at the Institute of Materials Science of Barcelona.

2.3. Gold nanoparticles synthesis and characterization

We have synthesized 20 nm diameter spherical AuNPs following the Turkevich method.³⁵ The synthesis is as follows: 50 mL of 0.25 mM HAuCl_4 solution are brought to boiling state; then, 1.25 mL of 38.75 mM sodium citrate solution are added in one shot; the colour mixture will change from colourless to purple and finally to dark red; once the AuNPs suspension becomes dark red the temperature is turned off; finally, when cooled down, the suspension is stored in the fridge.

AuNPs have been characterized by UV-Visible spectroscopy and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). 20 nm AuNPs exhibit a maximum absorbance peak at a wavelength of 520 nm,^{36,37} as it is shown in Fig. S1. TEM imaging demonstrated that the size of synthesized AuNPs was effectively 20 nm (Fig. S2).

2.4. DNA probes and synthetic miRNAs

Synthetic miRNA-638, miRNA-31-5p and DNA probes were obtained from Integrated DNA Technologies (IDT; Leuven, Belgium). DNA probes were designed to be complementary to the miRNA-638 according to Watson-Crick base pairing.³⁸ Thus, when present, half of miRNA-638 would hybridize with the DNA probe dispensed in the Test Line (TL) and the other half with the probe conjugated in the AuNPs, being thus captured in a sandwich between these 2 probes and leading to the appearance of the TL. DNA probe for the Control Line (CL) was designed to be complementary to the nanoparticle probe, working as control of the conjugation process and the correct flow of the test.

Sequences of the DNA probes, miRNA-638 and miRNA-31-5p are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. Sequences of the DNA probes used for lateral flow assay and the miRNA-638.

Name	Sequence (5'-3')
TL	amino-AAAAAAAAAAGCCGCCAC
CL	AGGGATCGCGGAAAAAAAAA-amino
NP	CCCGCATCCCTAAAAAAAAA-thiol*
MiRNA-638	AGGGAUCGCGGGCGGGUGGCGGCCU
MiRNA-31-5p	AGGCAAGAUGCUGGCAUAGCU

*Thiol Modifier C3 S-S (disulfide).

2.5. Lateral flow strips preparation

LF strips were assembled according to a protocol previously published,²⁴ composed by the four typical LF pads (sample, conjugate, detection and absorbent pad) immobilized on an adhesive laminated card. The strips were cut 4 mm width.

Sample and absorbent pads are composed by cellulose membrane, being the first one treated with 50 mM tris-buffered saline (TBS) at pH 7.6 containing 150 mM NaCl, 5 % BSA, 1 M betaine and 0.05% Tween 20.

Conjugate pad consists of glass fibre in which DNA-conjugated AuNPs suspension has been dried. DNA probes were acquired from IDT containing thiol groups in their oxidized form (disulfide), therefore requiring to be reduced for being conjugated on AuNPs. Tris (2-carboxyethyl) phosphine (TCEP) was used as reducing agent.^{39,40} 100 µL of 0.012 mM DNA probe were mixed during 1 h with 10 µL of 0.3 M freshly prepared TCEP to activate the thiol groups⁴¹ and then 1.2 mL of AuNPs were directly added and the mixture was incubated overnight. The suspension is centrifuged and resuspended in 200 µL of 1 mM borate buffer (BB, prepared by mixing boric acid and sodium tetraborate) at pH 7.4, containing a 10 % sucrose. This suspension is directly dispensed on glass fibre and dried. The ratio between the DNA probe and AuNPs was determined using the “gold aggregation test” (GAT) method;⁴² procedure detailed in the supporting information (Fig. S3-S5). AuNPs were selected as signal transducers due their striking red colour, consequence of its strong plasmon.⁴³

In the detection pad, high protein binding nitrocellulose membrane was employed. Instead of the usual approach of streptavidin-biotin,^{29,30,32} test and control amino-labelled DNA probes were used,²⁶ but in this case we used no crosslinker since, under the conditions we selected, we observed TL and CL remained stable and functional. Test and control amino-labelled DNA probes resuspended in 40 mM Tris-acetate and 1 mM ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) solution were dispensed with the continuous reagent dispenser at a concentration of 1 mg/mL and at a volume/line ratio of 0.50 µL/cm. DNA on nitrocellulose was dried at room temperature under dry conditions (i.e. in standard desiccator, overnight).

2.6. Lateral flow molecular assay

Serial dilutions of miRNA-638 were made in 0.06 M saline-sodium citrate buffer (SSC; i.e. 0.6 M NaCl in 0.06 M sodium citrate, pH 7.0) containing 1 % (w/v) 3-[(3-Cholamidopropyl)-dimethylamino]-propane-sulfonate (CHAPS). Same buffer was used as a blank. 120 µL of each dilution was tested by triplicate and after 15 min the LF strips were analysed by two methods for a quantitative analysis. By repeating the experiment several times, it was established that after 15 min signal is visible and it is not expected for it to appear later than this period of time.

The first method consisted in scanning all the strips with a standard PC scanner (HP DeskJet Plus scanner) in order to obtain an image to be analysed using ImageJ software.^{24,26,28} For the second method, Immunochromato reader (Hamamatsu) was used to scan each strip.

To evaluate the specificity of the assay, we conducted a test with another miRNA (non-related to ischemic stroke risk assessment), miRNA-31-5p, and compared its TL intensity to that of miRNA-638.

3. Results and discussion

miRNA-638 was serially diluted in 0.06 M SSC containing 1 % (w/v) CHAPS to the following concentrations: 0.122, 0.367, 1.220, 3.670, 12.20, 36.70 and 122.00 nM. 120 μ L of the dilutions and blank (0.06 M SSC, 1% CHAPS) were applied on the LF strips, by triplicate. Fig. 2 shows the optical response of the LF strips after 15 min of adding the sample.

Fig. 2. Optical response of the LF strips after 15 min. Serial dilutions of miRNA-638 in SSC 1 % CHAPS were tested in triplicates. The intensity of the TL increases as the concentration of miRNA-638 increments.

On Fig. 3 are represented the calibration curves obtained after analysing the data acquired with A) PC scanner and ImageJ, and B) Immunochromato reader. Both curves are quite similar in shape (obviating that the intensity values provided by each equipment have different ranges, since ImageJ values are limited in a range between 0-255), being the Immunochromato reader the more precise one (error bars are smaller).

The calculated equations resulted from each method are the following:

$$y = 23.911 \ln(x) + 32.423, R^2 = 0.9583 \text{ (A)}$$

$$y = 43.060 \ln(x) + 85.028, R^2 = 0.9913 \text{ (B)}$$

For each method, limit of detection (LoD) was calculated from the calibration equation by solving the “x” value when “y” is the “TL peak” or “TL height” value at blank (i.e. the average signal of blank, “b”) plus 3.3 times its standard deviation (σ).^{44,45} Therefore, the formula for the LoD is:

$$\text{LoD} = e^{(b + 3.3 \sigma - a)/m}$$

Being that “m” is the value multiplying the natural logarithm and “a” the value that intersects the ordinate axis in the calibration equation. The result was a LoD of 0.27 nM with the PC scanner and ImageJ, and 0.14 nM with the Immunochromato reader. These values agree with what can be observed at Fig. 2; positive response at 0.122 nM (under the LoD value) is not visible while at 0.367 nM (over the LoD value) a weak TL starts being visible.

If we consider only the lineal range of both calibration curves (between 0.122-3.670 nM) and we represent the lineal equations (graphics in supporting information, Fig. S6), we obtain that the sensitivity of the systems (i.e. the slope of the equation) is 14.142 for the scanner and 37.799 for the LF reader.

Fig. 3. Calibration curves obtained after analysing the data acquired with A) PC scanner and ImageJ software B) Immunochromato reader.

The specificity of the assay was evaluated by testing 100 ng/mL (14.76 nM) of a different miRNA (miRNA-31-5p), 100 ng/mL (12.20 nM) of miRNA-638 and the blank. The results are shown on Fig. 4, where it can be appreciated that there is no unspecific signal for miRNA-31-5p. It demonstrates that the signal produced on the TL occurs because of the DNA hybridization and not due to unspecific interactions of DNA on that nitrocellulose area.

It is noteworthy to emphasize that the strips remained functional even after being stored for a period of 15 months following their fabrication. It demonstrates that crosslinker is not necessary to immobilize amino-based DNA probes on nitrocellulose.

Fig. 4. Specificity test. Left: comparison of the TL intensity of blank, 100 ng/mL (14.76 nM) miRNA-31-5-p and 100 ng/mL (12.20 nM) miRNA-638. Right: picture of the corresponding LF strips.

4. Conclusions

We have successfully developed a DNA-based lateral LF assay capable of detecting miRNA-638, reaching a detection limit of 0.14 nM and a slope sensitivity of 37.799. Notably, this versatile design lays the foundation for potential applications in the detection of various other miRNAs, RNAs and

DNAs, including long non-coding RNA (lncRNA), by simply reconfiguring the capture DNA probes of our system. We must highlight that the real application and purpose of this system, although the LOD is really low for a LF system, is not based on the detection of the lowest concentration of miRNA, but in being able to evaluate when the standard values of miRNA-638 in a patient (which may be quite different from one healthy patient to another)^{13,14} are decreasing, since this is the factor that indicates that there is a risk to suffer an ischemic stroke.

By taking advantage of amino-labelled probes on a high protein-binding nitrocellulose membrane, we have devised a cost-effective and stable alternative to biotin-labelled probes that obviates the need for additional equipment or crosslinkers. This innovation represents a pivotal step toward democratizing diagnostic testing. While our results are already promising, there is room for further refinement to enhance detection limits.

The use of a chromatographic reader or simply a standard home scanner for quantitative analysis of the target allowed the quantitative determination of the target. The chromatographic reader exhibited superior precision, demonstrating nearly threefold increased sensitivity compared to the scanner. Nevertheless, both calibration curves displayed similar trends, validating the utility of a standard home scanner for quantifying assay responses.

In conclusion, our study not only introduces a robust miRNA detection platform but also lays the groundwork for a more accessible and cost-effective approach to RNA analysis, heralding a new era in biosensing technology and fast, affordable and democratized diagnostic.

Data availability

The data supporting this article have been included as part of the ESI.

Author contributions

Ana Rubio-Monterde: was involved in conceptualization, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, visualization and writing of the original draft. **Lourdes Rivas:** was involved in formal analysis, investigation and methodology. **Marc Gallegos:** was involved in conceptualization, funding acquisition and project administration. **Josep M. Aran:** was involved in conceptualization and funding acquisition. **Daniel Quesada-González:** was involved in conceptualization, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, funding acquisition, project administration, supervision, visualization and writing of the original draft and revised versions. **Arben Merkoçi** was involved in funding acquisition, supervision and manuscript revision.

Conflicts of interest

A. Rubio-Monterde and M. Gallegos are current employees of Paperdrop Diagnostics S.L.; L. Rivas and Daniel Quesada-González are former employees of Paperdrop Diagnostics S.L.; Arben Merkoçi holds the position of Chief Scientific Officer at Paperdrop Diagnostics S.L.; Josep M. Aran is a co-inventor of an issued patent¹³ on predictive methods of atherosclerosis and stenosis, which has been licensed to Paperdrop Diagnostics S.L.

Some experimental data might have been omitted to protect the future commercial interests of Paperdrop Diagnostics S.L. To request more information about the experiments or the status of the product, the company can be contacted at info@paperdropdx.com.

Acknowledgments

We acknowledge the funding received from the Ministerio de Economía y Competitividad (Madrid, Spain), which includes grants RTC-2017-6526-1 “RETOS-COLABORACIÓN” and DTS18/00086, and ISCIII, co-funded by FEDER funds/European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) “a way to build Europe”. We also thank the funding received from Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación (Madrid, Spain), which included grants PTQ2018-010113 “IRON” and DIN2018-010115 “LáMiNa”. We thank ACCIO financial support and mentoring services from the program STARTEC-18-1-0168. We thank CERCA Programme/Generalitat de Catalunya for institutional support and for grant 2017 SGR 00191. ICN2 is funded by CERCA programme, Generalitat de Catalunya. Grant SEV-2017-0706 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033. This project has also received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 951768, project MARVEL. Any dissemination of results reflects only the authors’ view and the European Commission Horizon 2020 is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information this manuscript contains.

A. Rubio-Monterde acknowledges Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB) for the possibility of performing this work inside the framework of Biotechnology PhD Programme. D. Quesada-González acknowledges Judith Oró-Solé from the Institute of Materials Science of Barcelona (ICMAB) for her assistance recording TEM images of nanomaterials. The authors would like to dedicate this work to the memory of Dr. Marina Cretich, who coordinated MARVEL Project and became a good friend; rest in peace, we miss you.

References

1. WHO. Integrating Stroke Services in Health Care Systems: A Practical Approach. 2020. <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/336231/9789290228134-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y> (last accessed 25/10/2023).
2. D. Mozaffarian, E.J. Benjamin, A.S. Go, et al., *Circulation*, 2016, **133**, 4, e38-e48.
3. A. Alonso, D. Artemis and M.G. Hennerici, *Cerebrovasc. Dis.*, 2015, **39**, 1, 5-12.
4. J. O’Brien, H. Hayder, Y. Zayed and C. Peng, *Front. Endocrinol.*, 2018, **9**, 1-12.
5. X. Chen, Y. Ba, L. Ma, et al., *Cell Res.*, 2008, **18**, 10, 997-1006.
6. P. S. Mitchell, R.K. Parkin, E.M. Kroh et al., *Proc. Natl. Acad. USA*, 2008, **105**, 30, 10513-10518.
7. S. Fichtlscherer, A.M. Zeiher and S. Dimmeler, *Arterioscler. Thromb. Vasc. Biol.*, 2011, **31**, 11, 2383-2390.
8. E. E. Creemers, A. J. Tijssen and Y. M. Pinto, *Circ. Res.*, 2019, **110**, 3, 483-495. doi:10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.111.247452.
9. L. N. Schulte, W. Bertrams, C. Stielow and B. Schmeck, *Methods Mol. Biol.*, 2019, **1912**, 3-32.
10. D. Loureiro, I. Tout, S. Narguet, S.M. Benazzouz, A. Mansouri, T. Asselah, *Viruses*, 2020, **12**, 12, 1440.
11. S. Bendifallah, S. Suisse, A. Puchar, et al., *J. Clin. Med.*, 2022, **11**, 3.
12. N. Garcia-Giralt, J. Du, J. Marin-Corral, et al., *Sci. Rep.*, 2022, **12**, 1, 6929.
13. J. M. Aran Perramon, A. Luque Gómez, J. Krupinski, Patent (EP3196317A1): Predictive methods of atherosclerosis and stenosis. Published online 2017.
14. A. Luque, A. Farwati, J. Krupinski and J.M. Aran, *J. Neurosurg.*, 2019, **131**, 1, 72-79.
15. V. P. Dave, T. A. Ngo, A. K. Pernestig, et al., *Lab. Investig.*, 2019, **99**, 4, 452-469.
16. D. Quesada-González, A. Merkoçi, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2018, **47**, 13, 4697-4709.
17. A. Merkoçi, C. Z. Li, L. M. Lechuga, A. Ozcan, *Biosens. Bioelectron.*, 2021, **178**, 113046.
18. A. Merkoçi, A., C. Z. Li, L. M. Lechuga, A. Ozcan, *Biosens Bioelectron.*, 2022, **212**, 114340.
19. A. Roda, S. Cavalera, F. Di Nardo, et al., *Biosens. Bioelectron.*, 2021, **172**, 112765.

20. J. H. Lee, M. Choi, Y. Jung, et al., *Biosens Bioelectron.*, 2021, **171**, 112715.
21. W. W. W. Hsiao, T. N. Le, D. M. Pham, et al., *Biosens.*, 2021, **11**, 9, 1-26.
22. F. Pei, S. Feng, W. Hu, B. Liu, X. Mu, Q. Hao, Y. Cao, W. Lei and Z. Tong, *Talanta*, 2023, **253**, 124051.
23. D. Quesada-González and A. Merkoçi, *Biosens Bioelectron.*, 2015, **73**, 47-63.
24. C. Parolo, A. Sena-Torralba, J.F. Bergua, et al., *Nat. Protoc.*, 2020, **15**, 12, 3788-3816.
25. D. Quesada-González and A. Merkoçi, *Sensor Technology Directory* (eBook), *Sensor100*, 2023, 3.1-3.5.
26. L. Rivas, P. Reuterswärd, R. Rasti et al., *Talanta*, 2018, **183**, 192-200.
27. D. Quesada-González and A. Merkoçi, *Biosens. Bioelectron.*, 2017, **92**, 549-562.
28. D. Quesada-González, G. A. Jairo, C. R. Blake, D. A. Blake and A. Merkoçi, *Sci. Rep.*, 2018, **8**, 1, 16157.
29. S. Y. Hou, Y. L. Hsiao, M. S. Lin, C. C. Yen and C. S. Chang, *Talanta*, 2012, **99**, 375-379.
30. X. Gao, H. Xu, M. Baloda, et al., *Biosens. Bioelectron.*, 2014, **54**, 578.
31. M. Jauset-Rubio, M. Svobodová, T. Mairal, et al., *Sci. Rep.*, 2016, **6**, 1, 1-10.
32. W. Zheng, L. Yao, J. Teng, et al., *Sens. Actuators B Chem.*, 2018, **264**, 320-326.
33. A. Rubio-Monterde, D. Quesada-González and A. Merkoçi, *Anal. Chem.* 2023, **95**, 1, 468-489.
34. E. Lamprou, M. Sotiriou, P. M. Kalligosfyri, D. P. Kalogianni, T. K. Christopoulos, *Talanta*, 2023, **262**, 124682.
35. J. Turkevich, P. C. Stevenson and J. Hillier, *Discuss. Faraday Soc.*, **1951**, 11, 55-75.
36. W. L. Barnes, A. Dereux and T. W. Ebbesen, *Nature*, 2003, **424**, 6950, 824-830.
37. A. Zuber, M. Purdey, E. Schartner, et al., *Sens. Actuators B Chem.*, 2016, **227**, 117-127.
38. F. H. C. Crick and J. D. Watson, *Proc. Math. Phys. Eng. Sci.*, 1954, **223**, 1152.
39. B. Liu, J. Liu, *Anal. Methods*, 2017, **9**, 18, 2633-2643.
40. R. Wu, L. P. Jiang, J. J. Zhu., J. Liu, *Langmuir*, 2019, **35**, 41, 13461-13468.
41. IDT, Reduction for oligonucleotides with thiol modifications. 2023 (last update). Guidelines: https://sfvideo.blob.core.windows.net/sitefinity/docs/default-source/protocol/reduction-protocol-for-thiol-modified-oligonucleotides.pdf?sfvrsn=431c3407_11 (last accessed 25/10/2023).
42. M. S. Cordray, M. Amdahl, R. R. Richards-Kortum, *Anal. Biochem.*, 2012, **431**, 2, 99-105.
43. K. Kant et al., *Nanoscale Horizons*, 2024, Just Accepted Manuscript, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D4NH00226A>
44. D.A. Armbruster and T. Pry, *Clin. Biochem. Rev.*, 2008, **29** Suppl. 1, S49-52.
45. H. Moulahoum and F. Ghorbanizamani, *Biosens. Bioelectron.*, 2024, **264**, 116670.